

Concept note: The multi-hazard context and its relevance to the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction / International Science Council's Hazard Information Profiles (HIPs)

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Abstract

At the intergovernmental level, including in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015), there is widespread acceptance that a '*multi-hazard*' approach is needed if risk reduction activities are to be more effective. An important development in recent years to support disaster risk management are the UNDRR/ISC Hazard information Profiles, commonly referred to as the HIPs. The first iteration of the HIPs (Murray et al., 2021) involved extensive consultation with scientists and experts around the world, generating 302 profiles for individual hazards.

In this initial iteration, the focus was on key information relevant to each individual hazard with limited attention to how these hazards may interrelate with one another. Yet, across diverse spatial scales, places are typically affected by more than one of the hazard types described in the HIPs. These hazards do not always occur independently, but can interrelate in various ways with other hazards, as well as other components of risk, vulnerability and exposure.

Here we bring together and synthesise a rich body of research, scholarship, and existing conceptual reviews to advance understanding of the multi-hazard concept. We particularly focus on the relevance of interrelationships that exist between different hazard types to diverse users of the HIPs. We argue that deepening this understanding of the multi-hazard concept, and applying it in the context of the HIPs, is critical for addressing the improvements called for in the 2023 Political Declaration of the High-Level Meeting on the Midterm Review of the Sendai Framework, and for supporting the full implementation of the Sendai Framework and successor frameworks. The HIPs have a key role in improving multi-hazard risk characterisation through ensuring a comprehensive approach and systematic use of hazard terminology. The inclusion of a multi-hazard context to each HIP strengthens further their usefulness, allowing reflection on how hazards interrelate and what complex hazard scenarios may be viable in any given place.

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1 Introduction

At the intergovernmental level, including in the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2015), there is widespread acceptance that a ‘multi-hazard’ approach is needed if risk reduction activities are to be effective. The 2023 Political Declaration of the High-Level Meeting on the Midterm Review of the Sendai Framework (UNDRR, 2023a) further calls for improvements to:

- The quality of and access to *multi-hazard risk data* in all sectors (article 16).
- The monitoring of systemic risk, cascading effects, compounding hazards and multiple risk drivers... sharing *good practices for multi-hazard risk assessment* (article 20).
- National and local *multi-hazard risk governance* (article 26).
- The use of *multi-hazard disaster risk assessments* (article 33).

An important development in recent years to support disaster risk management is the creation of the UNDRR/ISC Hazard information Profiles (Murray et al., 2021), hereafter referred to as the HIPs. The first iteration of the HIPs involved extensive consultation with scientists and experts around the world, generating 302 profiles for individual hazards. The HIPs are organised into eight thematic groups: Meteorological and Hydrological, Extraterrestrial, Geohazards, Environmental, Chemical, Biological, Technological, and Societal. In the first version of the HIPs, the focus was on key information relevant to each individual hazard with less emphasis on how these hazards may be interrelated. Across diverse spatial scales, places are typically exposed to more than one of the hazard types described in the HIPs (Claassen et al., 2023). These hazards do not always occur independently of one another but can interrelate with other hazards (Kappes et al., 2012; Gill and Malamud, 2014), as well as other components of risk, vulnerability and exposure (Duncan et al., 2016; Simpson et al., 2021). Not including hazard interrelationships can result in an underestimation of hazardousness and risk, distort management priorities, and may increase exposure and/or vulnerability to other hazards (Kappes et al., 2010).

The HIPs steering committee acknowledge these complexities and recognised that the next iteration of the HIPs should explore hazard interrelationships. To inform this process, the authors of this concept note have created this document which brings together and synthesises a rich body of research, scholarship, and existing conceptual syntheses and review papers (e.g., Kappes et al., 2012; Gill et al., 2022; Ward et al., 2022) on this topic to present the multi-hazard concept.

Here we briefly introduce the multi-hazard concept, including key definitions, types of hazard interrelationship, and a set of examples that demonstrate the relevance of the multi-hazard concept to diverse geographies and hazard types (Section 2). We then set out a summary of methods and future research priorities relating to understanding multi-hazards (Section 3), and explain why the multi-hazard concept is useful to different users (Section 4), such as academics, civil protection professionals, and urban planners. We finish by articulating why the multi-hazard concept is relevant to the HIPs and how an understanding of this concept, and lessons learned from multi-hazard research in recent decades, has informed the second iteration of the HIPs (Section 5).

2 The Multi-Hazard Concept

2.1 Origin of the Multi-Hazard Term

More than fifty years ago, Hewitt and Burton (1971, p. 5) advocated an ‘all-hazards-at-a-place’ framework, encouraging a ‘cross-hazard approach’ to understand the ‘hazardousness’ of a given location. In this work, Hewitt and Burton (1971) noted that most hazards research takes a single hazard approach, but that a greater emphasis on systematic ‘cross-hazard’ approaches is required. Hewitt and Burton (1971, p. 30) also characterised disasters as frequently involving multiple ‘agents’ (i.e., hazards), with these either occurring in a compound manner (e.g., wind, rain and lightning all occurring simultaneously during a storm) or occurring in succession (e.g., a hurricane can trigger a landslide and/or flooding). Over time, Hewitt and Burton’s ‘cross-hazard’ concept has

evolved into the ‘multi-hazard’ concept, widely referred to across key intergovernmental frameworks including:

1. **Agenda 21** (1992), the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development: pre-disaster planning should include “multi-hazard research into risk and vulnerability of human settlements and settlement infrastructure, including water and sewerage, communication and transportation networks, as one type of risk reduction may increase vulnerability to another” (UNCED, 1992).
2. **Johannesburg Plan of Implementation** (2002), noted “an inclusive, integrated and multi-hazard approach to tackle vulnerability, risk assessment and disaster management” (clause 37) (UN, 2002).
3. **Hyogo Framework for Action** (2005–15), requested “an integrated multi-hazard approach to DRR” (UNDRR, 2005, p. 4).
4. **Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction** (2015–30), states that “DRR needs to be multi-hazard” (UNDRR, 2015a, p. 10).

Despite the repeated use of the term ‘multi-hazard’ in successive intergovernmental agreements prior to the Sendai Framework, the term ‘multi-hazard’ was not included in the agreed UNDRR terminology (see Section 2.1) until 2016, when the UN General Assembly Report on the Open-Ended Intergovernmental Expert Working Group on indicators and terminology relating to disaster risk reduction proposed a definition (UNGA, 2016), which was adopted in 2017 (UNGA, 2017).

Formally adopting an agreed definition of the term ‘multi-hazard’ is important as it enables those implementing and monitoring progress against the Sendai Framework to have clarity as to what is necessary to fulfil its objectives relating to the term ‘multi-hazard’. For instance, characterising hazard interrelationships (Kappes et al., 2012; Gill and Malamud, 2014) rather than only analyse multiple independent hazards or superimpose various hazard layers to identify areas of spatial overlap (commonly applied approaches to characterising multi-hazards).

2.2 Hazard Interrelationship Terminology and Types

In 2016, UNDRR defined ‘multi-hazard’ to mean “(1) the selection of multiple major hazards that the country faces, and (2) the specific contexts where hazardous events may occur simultaneously, cascadingly or cumulatively over time, and taking into account the potential interrelated effects.” UNDRR (2016). In this context, multi-hazard approaches are considered to include but extend beyond the collation (or overlay) of distinct information for multiple single hazards (or ‘multi-layer single hazard’ approaches), to also characterise the relationships between hazards.

A range of terms are used in the literature to collectively describe the spatial and temporal links between hazards (e.g. interrelationships, interactions, interconnections, see Greiving 2006; Tarvainen et al. 2006; de Pippo et al. 2008; Perles Roselló and Cantarero Prados, 2010; Zuccaro and Leone 2011; Kappes et al., 2012; Gill and Malamud, 2014; Duncan et al. 2016; Ciurean et al., 2018; Tilloy et al., 2019; Zscheischler et al., 2020; Simpson et al., 2021; de Angeli et al., 2022; Claassen et al., 2023).

The term ‘interrelationships’ aligns with the UNDRR (2016) definition and is adopted in this article. Reviews of different interrelationships in the academic literature (e.g., Ciurean et al. 2018; Gill et al., 2022) identified many commonalities between the range of terms used in the literature, with three typical types of hazard interrelationship described below:

- **Triggering Relationships.** One hazard event causes one or more other hazard events to occur, which may then trigger additional hazardous events (Kappes et al., 2012). For example,
 - a tropical storm results in the destabilisation and collapse of a slope generating a mud flow;
 - a landslide triggered by a tropical storm blocks a river causing a temporary dam, with a flash flood triggered when this dam is breached;

- a tropical storm triggers drain and sewer flooding, which results in an outbreak of cholera.
- *Amplification Relationships*. One hazard can change the likelihood and/or magnitude of additional hazards in the future. For example,
 - drought increases the likelihood of wildfires;
 - wildfires, in turn, can then alter watershed conditions and subsequently increase the magnitude of floods and the likelihood of debris flows.
- *Compound Relationships*. Two or more hazards may impact the same region and/or time period with impacts different (greater, lesser) than their sum (de Ruiter et al., 2020; Zscheischler et al., 2020). These compound relationships can take different forms, including (i) multiple (triggered) hazards occurring simultaneously, or (ii) two independent hazards impacting the same region and/or time period (or in close succession). For example,
 - floods and landslides (both arising from a tropical storm) occurring simultaneously;
 - an earthquake coinciding with a period of extreme cold;
 - an earthquake followed by a tropical storm.

These three interrelationship types can combine and result in complex multi-hazard events over both the short and long-term. For example, a volcanic eruption can *trigger* a wildfire, which in turn *amplifies* the likelihood and magnitude of a debris flow if heavy rain occurs soon after. An earthquake can *trigger* landslides and *amplify* the likelihood of future landslides in the event of another earthquake or monsoon.

Using the timeline of the Gongbatongsha Lake (Poiqu Basin, Eastern Himalaya) 2015 disaster, Satter et al., (2022) demonstrated that hazard interrelationships over both short- and long-term timescales can contribute to a disaster event. In this case, heavy precipitation *triggered* a slope failure above the Gongbatongsha Lake, with deposition of debris into the lake that *triggered* a glacial lake outburst flood. The flood entrained sediment from the valley floor, increasing its ability to erode the base of slopes. Much of this sediment was present as a result of the 25 April 2015, Mw 7.8 Gorkha earthquake (i.e., the earthquake *triggered* landslides, increasing the availability of sediment and thus *amplifying* the magnitude of future floods). The debris-rich flood moving down the valley from the Gongbatongsha Lake *triggered* additional landslides (Sattar et al., 2022).

A hazard may also *reduce* the likelihood of another hazard occurring (Gill and Malamud, 2014; Duncan et al., 2016, Tilloy et al., 2019). For example, a tropical storm with intense rainfall can extinguish wildfires and reduce the likelihood of them occurring in the immediate future. Heavy rain during a period of drought (while potentially triggering floods) can reduce the severity of the drought. While noted here for comprehensiveness, this type of interrelationship where a hazard is reduced by another is less likely to be accounted for in risk assessment and management. This is, in part, due to a tendency adopt a conservative approach to risk assessment) (Aven, 2016).

2.3 Multi-Hazard Examples

Multi-hazard interrelationships can be observed in many geographical contexts around the world. In Table 1 we briefly characterise 20 diverse multi-hazard case studies. The examples described in Table 1 are taken from multiple continents, a period stretching from 1930 (ID-1) to 2023 (ID-20). For each example we note a location and year associated with the event but recognise that some case studies extended over multiple territories and years. We also include an overview and references for each example.

Table 1. Multi-Hazard Interrelationship Examples. Diverse case studies that demonstrate the prevalence of hazard interrelationships, with a location, year and overview stated for each of the 20 examples, along with references.

ID	Location	Year	Overview	Reference(s)
1	Merapi, Indonesia	1930–31	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The infiltration of heavy rain may have destabilised the volcanic dome and triggered phreatomagmatic eruptions. 2. Further heavy rain triggered lahars. 	Voight et al. (2000)
2	Huascarán, Peru	1970	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earthquake triggered rock and ice fall. 2. Rock and ice accumulated further material while travelling downslope, the ice/snow melted, and a mud-rich debris flow formed. 	Evans et al. (2009)
3	Nevado del Ruiz, Columbia	1985	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Volcanic eruption triggered snow/ice melting. 2. Snow and ice melt combined with debris to form lahars. 3. Lahars triggered structural failure and land degradation. 	Pierson et al. (1990)
4	Pinatubo, Philippines	1991	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coincidence of volcanic eruption with Typhoon Yunya resulted in lahars and structural failures (wet ash-laden roofs). 2. Lahars blocked rivers, causing flooding. 	Leone and Gaillard (1999); Newhall (2021)
5	Mt Cook, New Zealand	1991	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Warm temperatures triggered snowmelt. 2. Snowmelt triggered a large snow avalanche and landslide. 	Huggel et al. (2010)
6	Northridge, USA	1994	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earthquake triggered more than 11,000 landslides. 2. Landslides blocked roads and hampered relief efforts. 	Harp & Jibson (1996)
7	Umbria, Italy	1996–97	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rapid temperature increase triggered the melting of snow from a recent snowstorm. 2. Snowmelt triggered many landslides. 	Cardinali et al. (2000)
8	Chi-Chi, Taiwan	1999	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earthquake triggered 1000s of landslides, ground heave and large aftershocks. 2. Earthquake triggered structural failures, infrastructure failures (bridge / dam failure). 	Shin and Teng (2001)
9	Zhouqu, China	2010	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Heavy rain triggered a large debris flow. 2. Debris flow blocked a river and triggered floods. 	Tang et al. (2011)
10	Maule, Chile	2010	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earthquake triggered a tsunami and multiple aftershocks. 	Wilson et al. (2010)
11	Tohoku, Japan	2011	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earthquake triggered tsunami, ground subsidence and landslides. 2. Tsunami triggered floods. 3. Flooding caused multiple infrastructure failures. 	Mimura et al. (2011); Mori et al. (2012); Ranghieri et al. (2014)
12	Rwenzori Mountains, Uganda	2013	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wildfires resulted in loss of vegetation and increase in surface runoff during heavy rain. 2. High river discharge resulted in (re)activation of landslides, providing debris to the river system, and triggering a debris-rich flash flood. 3. The flood destroyed buildings and caused bridge failure. 	Jacobs et al. (2016)

ID	Location	Year	Overview	Reference(s)
13	France	2015-16	1. Abnormally warm temperatures in late autumn and abnormally wet conditions the following spring, leading to extreme crop yield losses.	Ben-Ari et al. (2018)
14	Texas, USA	2017	1. Compound flooding from Hurricane Harvey due to combination of high wind speeds, extreme rainfall, and elevated coastal water levels over several days.	Valle-Levinson et al. (2020); Huang et al. (2021)
15	Beira, Mozambique	2019	1. Compound flooding from Tropical Storms Idai (which in turn came with extreme winds and precipitation) and Kenneth. 2. Cholera outbreak and other infectious diseases. This was exacerbated by a lack of sanitation and access to clean drinking water, especially in densely populated, poorer regions.	WHO (2019); van Berchum et al. (2020); Domingos Lequechane et al (2020)
16	Afghanistan	2019	1. Heavy rainfall and rapid snowmelt leading to extensive floods. 2. Followed by disease outbreak (diarrhoea).	iMMAP (2019); ACAPS (2019)
17	California, USA	2020-23	1. Prolonged drought period between 2020-2022 which amplified wildfires. 2. Followed by torrential rain from consecutive atmospheric rivers around New Year 2022/2023, triggering floods and landslides. 3. Floods amplified by previous drought and wildfire conditions due to reduced soil water holding capacity. 4. Floods amplified chance of flooding in following year due to increased vegetation regrowth and therefore fuel.	CNN (2023); DeFlorio et al. (2024); Purohit (2025)
18	Haiti	2021	1. Large earthquake followed by Tropical Depression Grace 2 days later, hampering humanitarian and response efforts. 2. Thousands of landslides triggered. 3. A year later a cholera outbreak followed.	Eberle (2022); Whitworth et al. (2022); Amatya et al. (2023); Hadeed et al., 2023
19	Northwestern Europe and northern Central Europe	2022	1. Series of three winter storms (Dudley, Eunice, Franklin) within a period of about a week, affecting the same regions consecutively.	Mühr et al. (2022)
20	Slovenia	2023	1. Extreme rainfall generated by storms over several days causing river floods and triggering extensive landslides. 2. Floods amplified by high soil moisture due to antecedent conditions after several wetter than usual months.	Bezak et al. (2023)

For necessary brevity, the contents of Table 1 are limited to 20 examples. Many more examples are described in the academic literature, in government and technical reports, and in the media. While the examples in Table 1 focus on the hazard interrelationships, Section 2.4 notes that interrelationships between hazards and other components of risk (i.e., exposure, vulnerability) are also possible.

2.4 Interrelationships with other Risk Components

The focus of this concept note is to demonstrate that interrelationships exist between different hazard types and why the integration of a multi-hazard context into the revised HIPs is beneficial to

diverse users. However, this multi-hazard context is only one part of a wider multi-risk system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of 'Dynamic Risk' Equation. A representation of risk, shown as a function $f []$ of hazard, exposure, vulnerability, and time (t), where terms are not simply multiplied and interactions between them are recognised. As each of the three terms and their interactions can change over time (i.e., they are dynamic), this equation also includes a time variable. Thick up-down arrows represent changing levels of risk, hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. Thin left-right arrows represent interrelationships between the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability terms. Source: Gill et al. (2021) CC BY 4.0 © BGS (UKRI) and KCL

As demonstrated above, risk and its components are dynamic, changing through time and interrelating with one another to shape risk (Duncan et al., 2016; de Ruiter et al., 2020; Gill et al., 2021; Simpson et al., 2021; de Ruiter and van Loon, 2022, Ward et al., 2022).

Hazards can result in, and be influenced by, changes in exposure and/or vulnerability (Duncan et al., 2016, de Ruiter et al., 2020). Where the occurrence of hazards changes the exposure and/or vulnerability to another hazard, this can result in greater impacts than if only the first hazard had occurred (Simpson et al., 2021). For example:

- Infrastructure development (*exposure*) can change the likelihood or magnitude of flooding (*hazard*), through creating impermeable surfaces and reducing infiltration.
- Increases in corruption levels or reduced compliance with forestry legislation (*vulnerability*) can exacerbate illegal deforestation, increasing the likelihood or magnitude of landslides (*hazard*).
- Increased settlement (*exposure*) on slopes susceptible to landslides, without access to suitable waste management planning (*vulnerability*) can degrade natural drainage, increasing the likelihood or magnitude of landslides (*hazard*).
- An earthquake (*hazard*) can damage infrastructure (*exposure*), weakening the structural stability (physical *vulnerability*) so that it is more likely to be impacted by a consecutive event, such as a tropical storm (*hazard*).

Hazards can transform exposure and vulnerability in complex, non-linear ways. Hazards can shift vulnerable populations into highly exposed regions, or damage protective infrastructure, creating and exacerbating existing risk pathways (de Ruiter et al., 2020; Hochrainer-Stigler et al., 2023). For example, Bartel and Naismith (2023) write about the threats to livelihoods and social networks (changes to vulnerability) that arose from the evacuation and resettlement (changes to exposure) of people during the 7-8 March 2022 paroxysmal eruption (hazard) of Fuego volcano, Guatemala.

3 Hazard Interrelationship Methods and Visualisations

The classification and characterisation of hazard interrelationships has been explored through both qualitative and quantitative approaches. These approaches have been extensively reviewed by others, and it is beyond the scope of this concept note to outline these in detail. Here we direct the reader to some key resources that will support their understanding of methods for characterising and visualising hazard interrelationships.

Ciurean et al., (2018) reviewed the academic literature and set out key approaches used to understand either a multi-hazard landscape or the potential damage to assets by multi-hazard events. Examples of tools in the Ciurean et al., (2018) review (with examples from the academic literature) include narrative descriptions or storytelling (e.g., Han et al., 2007), hazard wheels (e.g., Appelquist and Halsnæs, 2015), hazard matrices (e.g., Tarvainen et al., 2006; Kappes et al., 2010; Gill et al., 2020; Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2024; Thompson et al., 2025, Figure 2), network diagrams (e.g., Van Westen et al., 2014), maps (e.g., Johnson et al., 2016; Lindsay and Robertson, 2018), indices (e.g., Araya-Muñoz et al., 2017; White et al., 2024), systems based or physical modelling (e.g., Chen et al., 2016), and probabilistic and statistical approaches (e.g., Neri et al., 2013; Mignan et al., 2014; Claassen et al., 2023). This latter category is expanded on by Tilloy et al. (2019) in their extensive review of quantification methodologies for multi-hazard interrelationships. Tilloy et al., (2019) identified 19 different modelling methods to quantify natural hazard interrelationships, grouped into three broad types: stochastic, empirical, and mechanistic. Work to increase the visibility and accessibility of multi-hazard approaches includes the MYRIAD-EU output ‘Disaster Risk Gateway’ (© BGS (UKRI) CC by 4.0) (<https://disasterriskgateway.net/>), which is a wiki for discovery and sharing of approaches for multi hazard risk assessment and management.

Figure 2. Example of a 23-cell x 23-cell multi-hazard interrelationship matrix developed for the Kathmandu Valley (Nepal) (from Thompson et al., 2025). Primary hazards are on the y axis, secondary hazards are on the x axis, and the hazards are coded as detailed in the legend on the right. The matrix shows where a primary hazard triggers a secondary hazard (upper left triangle shaded), a primary hazard increases the probability of (amplifies) a secondary hazard (lower right triangle shaded), a primary hazard both triggers and increases the probability of (amplifies) a secondary hazard (both triangles shaded), and where evidence is found for the interrelationship influencing the Kathmandu Valley (white letter E). This figure is an adaptation of the visualisation and classification methodology

developed by Gill and Malamud (2014). Image © Thompson et al., 2025, used under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>).

4 How Multi-Hazard Information in the HIPs can Support Risk Reduction

Recognising the significant extent of interrelationships within hazardous events, this section explores how information about hazard interrelationships can be leveraged to support risk reduction efforts. Characterising multi-hazard interrelationships, and embedding understanding of such dynamics into the HIPs, will support users (e.g., academics, civil protection professionals, urban planners, insurance companies, community-based organisation) to recognise complex hazard dynamics. Gill et al. (2020) outline the benefits of enhanced multi-hazard interrelationship information for individuals working on any hazard to place their work within the context of other natural hazards and help to support communication between different stakeholders. As such, we suggest that enhanced multi-hazard interrelationship knowledge - offered through the revised HIPs - can support the following (and more) activities:

- 1. Early Warning.** Despite global initiatives like Early Warnings for All (UN, 2025), significant gaps remain in implementing effective Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems (MHEWS), particularly in ensuring systems are people-centred and address the needs of vulnerable populations in the Global South (Rokhideh et al., 2025; Budimir et al., 2025). In many cases, operational multi-hazard early warning systems (MHEWS) are limited to the inclusion of discrete individual hazards and to date largely do not accommodate the complexity of hazard interrelationships. Developing Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems (MHEWS) that truly address multiple hazards simultaneously, and their interrelationships, could allow for the harmonisation of approaches across risk monitoring, communication, dissemination, preparedness, and response (UNDRR and WMO, 2024). Some of the advances of such an approach, as stated by UNDRR (2023b), potentially include the minimisation of inefficiencies, lower maintenance costs, avoidance of duplication, and thereby allowing for the maximisation of investments in awareness, education, and preparedness. To do this, a ‘system of systems’ approach can be useful, bringing together pre-existing EWS (UNDRR and WMO, 2024), with work required to ensure interrelationships are then embedded.
- 2. Land-use and development planning.** Characterising potential multi-hazard interrelationships and scenarios can help inform appropriate land-use planning (Gill et al., 2021). Understanding the spatial distribution of multiple hazards, and how hazards may propagate from one region to another as a result of interrelationships, can inform spatial planning and the actions that may be needed to reduce risk. In some contexts, the extension or initiation of anthropogenic activities (e.g., vegetation removal, dewatering, subsurface construction, quarrying) to facilitate urban expansion may trigger or exacerbate multi-hazard scenarios (Gill et al., 2017). For example, dewatering in a coastal city may result in subsidence, which increases the likelihood of storm surge flooding. Understanding potential hazard interrelationships supports stakeholders to understand and manage current and future risks through comprehensive risk management strategies, anticipating future scenarios, as advocated for in the 2025 Global Platform for Disaster Risk Reduction concept note (UNDRR, 2025).
- 3. Design of efficient and effective risk reduction strategies.** Understanding multi-hazard scenarios can inform more effective risk reduction planning (at local, regional, national, multi-national scales). Identifying interventions that reduce the risk from multiple hazards or act early in a hazard chain may help to reduce the propagation of additional hazards, thus reducing the overall impact of a multi-hazard scenario (Gill et al., 2021). For example, since a storm may trigger landslides and floods, investment in effective drainage measures would be an efficient risk reduction intervention as this reduces the storm’s likelihood of triggering landslides and flooding. Furthermore, by embracing a multi-hazard approach, one can start to identify any trade-offs or asynergies (i.e., interventions that reduce vulnerability and exposure to one hazard while increasing vulnerability and exposure to another hazard) (de Ruiter et al., 2021). A coherent approach to risk management also reduces the risk of ‘fatigue’ and

inaction, which could be experienced if a community (for example) are presented with different risk reduction strategies for each hazard.

4. **Strengthening cross-organisational (or cross-hazard) communication mechanisms.** The process of constraining multi-hazard interrelationships can help to strengthen communication across organisations responsible for different hazards or different aspects of risk reduction (Gill et al., 2020; Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2024; Thompson et al., 2025). A collaborative approach to identifying relevant hazards, mapping out potential interrelationships, and determining key scenarios can help to build and strengthen collective understanding of hazard interrelationships, building the strong institutions and cross-departmental and cross-disciplinary communication required for effective multi-hazard risk governance (Scolobig et al., 2017). For example, a potential scenario affecting a city could be an earthquake and tropical cyclone occurring in quick succession, both damaging the city's water and waste infrastructures, resulting in one or more waterborne diseases (e.g., cholera). For a city to prepare for and respond to this scenario, relevant actors (e.g., meteorologists, hydrologists, seismologists, epidemiologists, engineers, fire departments, civil protection agencies and others) would need to work together. These professions may or may not sit within different organisations or agencies. Identifying multi-hazard scenarios is a way to bring these groups together in advance of any event taking place, initiating dialogue and improving clarity around roles and responsibilities, and strengthening trust and cooperation.
5. **Response Actions.** One hazard can change the likelihood and/or magnitude of additional hazards in the future (*amplification relationships*). Using this multi-hazard information can improve disaster response, by ensuring careful consideration is given to which additional hazards may now be more likely to occur. For example, in the event of a wildfire, people or assets may need to be relocated to another region. Understanding that wildfires increase the likelihood of debris flows and/or the magnitude of floods (and the topography / drainage pattern of the specific locality) will inform appropriate siting of temporary or permanent resettlement facilities, ensuring that exposure and vulnerability of displaced people are not increased.
6. **Integrating Policy.** Policy formulation and implementation processes increasingly recognise the importance of multi-hazard approaches, particularly as governments confront the limitations of siloed risk governance. A central role in shaping national policies - informing strategic decision-making, resource allocation, and cross-government preparedness planning - is played by National Risk Assessments (NRAs). Such instruments, like the UK's National Security Risk Assessment (NSRA), provide a structured approach to understanding and prioritising risks, including natural hazards, but have historically faced challenges in integrating hazard interrelationships and cascading risks across sectors and policies (Schlumberger et al., 2023). In the UK, the evolution of the NSRA and its public counterpart, the National Risk Register (NRR, 2025), reflects a gradual shift from a single-hazard focus toward a more integrated understanding of multi-hazard dynamics, including cascading effects (e.g., disruption to transport networks, supply chains, power supplies and water supplies due to high temperatures and heatwaves) and cross-sectoral impacts (e.g., a nationwide loss of power resulting in secondary impacts across critical utilities networks causing significant and widespread disruption to public services provisions, businesses and households, as well as loss of life). The NSRA provides a unified risk evidence base that informs policy responses across multiple areas (e.g., national security, climate adaptation, public health, infrastructure resilience) by recognising how chronic and acute risks intersect (e.g., climate change leading to an increased frequency and severity of weather events that cause floods and wildfires). However, the integration of multi-hazard interrelationships into policy instruments remains an area requiring further development to support coordinated, cross-government decision-making.

These examples demonstrate some of the benefits of multi-hazard interrelationship information in informing and improving disaster risk reduction efforts. In recent years we have seen examples of

the development of comprehensive, systematic, and evidenced characterisations of multi-hazard interrelationships for defined spatial regions, including:

- *National scales*. Guatemala (Gill et al., 2020), Sweden (Gustafsson et al., 2023).
- *City scales*. Istanbul, Turkey (Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2024), Nairobi, Kenya (Šakić Trogrlić et al., 2024) and the Kathmandu Valley (Thompson et al., 2025).

Acknowledged in these studies is the inherent uncertainty in anticipating how hazards may interact, particularly in complex environments where triggering and compound relationships can evolve in variable ways. The frameworks set out in the studies relating to Guatemala, Sweden, Nairobi (Kenya), Istanbul (Turkey), and Kathmandu (Nepal) use evidence to describe what has the potential to occur more generally - but anticipating which multi-hazard scenarios might occur, when these might occur, and how intense the hazards could be in a given place and time remains challenging. Nevertheless, active reflection on the multi-hazard context and potential multi-hazard scenarios can strengthen our collective ability to navigate that uncertainty (e.g., through building the required institutional mechanisms to navigate responses to multi-hazard events).

5 Conclusion

The inclusion of a multi-hazard context to each HIP strengthens further their usefulness, allowing reflection on how hazards interrelate and what complex hazard scenarios may be viable in any given place. As suggested in Section 4, we believe this has several tangible benefits that will support implementation of the Sendai Framework and the substantial reduction of disaster risk and losses of all types.

A detailed rationale for the approach taken in the HIPs to represent the multi-hazard context is beyond the scope of this concept note or the responsibility of the authors. This is likely to be set out in detail in the publications associated with the 2025 updated HIPs. The use of exemplars of hazard interrelationships demonstrates the importance of thinking across hazards and encourages active reflection on what multi-hazard interrelationships may be relevant (supporting users to reflect on the multi-hazard concept in their work and contexts). In the future, each HIP could include a comprehensive characterisation of how that hazard interrelates with other hazards. While clearly beneficial to the wider risk management community, the work to achieve this would be resource intensive. Being 'comprehensive' is different to being 'complete'. The former recognises the inherent uncertainties that exist in hazard interrelationships and our ability to map these out in an exhaustive manner (Gill and Malamud, 2014). Any included overview of hazard interrelationships is unlikely to cover all possible combinations, with critical active reflection on the multi-hazard context required by users of the HIPs.

The development and inclusion of multi-hazard information into the HIPs, and the ongoing reflection and updating of this information as the HIPs are reviewed over time, is a welcome 'mainstreaming' of the multi-hazard approach.

6 References

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